

ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED SINGLE LAP JOINTS IN SRIM COMPOSITES UNDER FLEXURAL LOADING

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SUMMARY: This paper presents the results of a study carried out on adhesively bonded single lap joints between two SRIM composite substrates subjected to flexural loading. The flexural loading was created by deflecting the free end of a cantilever beam constructed of two SRIM substrates joined together by a thin layer of adhesive. Non-linear finite element analysis was used to determine the stress distributions in the adhesive as well as the substrates. The effects of substrate stiffness on the maximum longitudinal, transverse (peel) and shear stresses were determined. Deflection-controlled fatigue tests were conducted on a cantilever beam containing an adhesively bonded single lap joint between two SRIM substrates of various stiffnesses. Regions of high stress areas identified by the finite element analysis show good correlation with the location of failure initiation observed in fatigue tests.

KEYWORDS: adhesive joints, single lap specimens, flexural loading, fatigue failure

INTRODUCTION

The most common test method for adhesive joints is the single lap joint test in which a tensile load is applied to the substrates [1]. In this mode of loading, the adhesive is subjected to both direct shear stress as well as stresses due to a small amount of bending created by the eccentricity of tensile loads acting at the ends of the substrates. There are many practical applications where the substrates may be subjected to large flexural loads. While single lap joints under tensile loads have been studied both analytically and experimentally, there are no reported studies on single lap joints under flexural loads.

In this paper, we have considered the behavior of adhesively bonded single lap joints in a randomly oriented continuous fiber reinforced SRIM composite under flexural loading. The flexural load was created by deflecting the free end of a cantilever beam constructed by adhesively joining two SRIM substrates. Several different substrate thickness combinations were considered to examine the effect of substrate stiffness on the stress distribution in the joint.

Finally, a few experimental results involving cyclic flexure load are described. These experiments were conducted principally to observe the failure modes in flexural fatigue cycling.

BASIC SPECIMEN CONFIGURATIONS

The basic specimen configuration used in this study is shown in Fig 1. It consists of a cantilever beam specimen prepared by joining two 25-mm wide, 3.2-mm thick SRIM substrates. The SRIM material contains randomly oriented continuous E-glass fiber mat reinforcement in a polyisocyanurate resin. The fiber content in the composite is 40 percent by weight. The two substrates are bonded together over a lap length of 12.7 mm. The bond thickness is 0.762 mm and the lap width is 25 mm. The unbonded end of the shorter bottom substrate (henceforth called substrate 1) is clamped by a narrow steel bar to a 70 mm long x 50 mm wide x 6.35 mm thick aluminum plate, which in turn is fixed at its left end. The unbonded end of the long top substrate in the SRIM-SRIM cantilever beam specimen (henceforth called substrate 2) is deflected first in the upward direction to a maximum deflection of 25.4 mm and then in the downward direction, also to a maximum deflection of 25.4 mm.

Several different substrate thickness conditions (t_1 and t_2 represent thickness of substrate 1 and 2, respectively) were considered in this study.

- (a) $t_1 = t_2 = 3.2$ mm.
- (b) $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2$ mm
- (c) $t_1 = 3.2$ mm and $t_2 = 6.4$ mm
- (d) $t_1 = t_2 = 6.4$ mm
- (e) $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2$ mm in the lap area, but $t_2 = 6.4$ mm outside the lap area
- (f) $t_1 = 3.2$ mm in the lap area, but $t_1 = 6.4$ mm outside the lap area. Similarly, $t_2 = 3.2$ mm in the lap area, but $t_2 = 6.4$ mm outside the lap area.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Modeling

Two-dimensional non-linear finite element analysis was conducted using ANSYS 5.3, a general purpose finite element package available from ANSYS, Inc. Geometric non-linearity was considered in this analysis to account for substrate rotation in the lap area. All three materials, namely the SRIM, adhesive and aluminum alloy, were assumed to behave in a linear elastic and isotropic manner in response to mechanical loads. Properties used in the analysis for SRIM, epoxy adhesive and aluminum alloy were: modulus = 9.32, 3.81 and 70 GPa and Poisson's ratio = 0.352, 0.48 and 0.33. Since the specimen width was much greater than the adhesive thickness, a plane strain condition was assumed.

Eight-noded isoparametric quadrilateral elements with two degrees of freedom at each node (i.e., U_x and U_y) were used. Finer mesh was used in regions of high stresses or stress singularities, such as the adhesive-substrate interface, sharp corners at the substrate ends and the spew ends. The length of the aluminum plate (70 mm), the length of SRIM substrate 1 (38.1 mm), the length of SRIM substrate 2 (82.55 mm), the lap length between the SRIM substrates (12.7 mm) and the adhesive thickness (0.762 mm) were kept constant for all of the beam configurations considered. The spew at each lap end was assumed to have a quarter round shape with a radius equal to the substrate thickness at that end.

To simulate up and down deflection of the beam, the U_y displacement of the right end of substrate 2 was increased in time steps along three linear segments. The first segment consists of an upward deflection from zero to +25.4 mm, the second segment starts from +25.4 mm and decreases to -25.4 mm and the third segment extends from -25.4 mm to zero deflection. Each step in the stepwise deflection increment represents 20 percent of the total deflection in each direction.

During the upward deflection of the specimen, substrate 1 bends away from the aluminum plate, thus opening up a small separation between them. However, during the downward deflection, there is a continuous contact between the aluminum plate and substrate 1 as they bend together. To account for the separation during the upward deflection and contact during the downward deflection, contact elements were used at the interface between the aluminum plate and substrate 1. Contact elements have negligible stiffness during the upward deflection, which allows a free deformation of substrate 1 away from the interface. However, during the downward deflection, the contact elements behave as stiff links between the aluminum plate and substrate 1. In our study, triangular contact elements, each containing one target node and two contact nodes, were used at the interface. The target nodes were on the aluminum side of the interface and the contact nodes were on the substrate 1 side of the interface.

Stresses in the Adhesive Layer

Fig. 2 shows the stress distributions in the adhesive layer for a specimen with equal substrate thickness of 3.2 mm on both sides of the adhesive joint. Axial (σ_{xx}), peel (σ_{yy}) and shear (τ_{xy}) stresses are plotted as a function of distance from the left end of the joint along the interface $A_1B_1C_1D_1$ as well as the adhesive mid-thickness for a 25.4 mm downward end deflection. As seen in this figure, the downward deflection creates tensile σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} at the left end A_1 of the interface. Both these normal stresses as well as the shear stress reach their maximum values at A_1 and reduce rapidly to near-zero values within the left spew length (A_1B_1). At the right end of the interface, the stresses are relatively low. At the mid-thickness, axial (σ_{xx}) and peel (σ_{yy}) stresses are also tensile at the left side of the joint, but their maximum values occur slightly inside the spew. Similarly, the maximum value of the shear stress (τ_{xy}) at the adhesive mid-thickness is slightly inside the spew. The upward deflection reverses the stress directions and also creates slightly different maximum values from those obtained during the downward deflection.

For single lap joints subjected to flexural loading, the stress distributions in the adhesive, either at the interface or at the mid-thickness, are not symmetric relative to the center of the lap length. If the single lap joint is subjected to axial loading instead of flexural loading, the stress distributions at the interface are also unsymmetric, but the stress distributions at the mid-thickness are symmetric.

Although the nature of stress distributions is very similar in all of the cases considered here, the maximum values of σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and τ_{xy} are quite different. The maximum stresses are much higher at the adhesive-SRIM interface than at the adhesive mid-thickness. The maximum σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and τ_{xy} at the interface (Table 1) have their lowest values for the beam specimen with $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2$ mm. The maximum stresses for this beam specimen are even lower than for the beam specimen with $t_1 = t_2 = 3.2$ mm. The maximum stresses for the beam specimen with $t_1 = 3.2$ mm and $t_2 = 6.4$ mm are considerably higher than the beam specimen with $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2$

mm. All three stresses, σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and τ_{xy} , are nearly doubled when both substrate thickness is increased from 3.2 to 6.4 mm.

The differences in maximum stress values in various beam configurations can be explained in terms of the difference in substrate deformations, which in turn, are related to the difference in substrate stiffness. Table 2 lists the vertical loads required to cause a 25.4-mm upward end deflection in each beam specimen. These vertical loads were calculated using the finite element analysis and they represent the vertical nodal load at the right specimen end. Table 2 also lists the vertical loads determined using strain gages that were mounted on the aluminum plate. As can be seen from Table 2, vertical loads determined in these two ways are within 10 percent of each other, which, in a way, is a validation of the finite element analysis conducted in this study.

From Table 2, it can be observed that the end load increases five folds when the thickness of both substrates is increased from 3.2 mm to 6.4 mm. In other words, a beam specimen with $t_1 = t_2 = 6.4$ mm is five times stiffer than a beam specimen with $t_1 = t_2 = 3.2$ mm. It is interesting to note that if this was a straight beam instead of a stepped beam with a single lap adhesive joint, the stiffness increase would have been eight fold instead of five fold. As expected, increasing the thickness of either substrate 1 or substrate 2 from 3.2 mm to 6.4 mm causes a much lower increase in specimen stiffness. The end load data in Table 2 indicate that the difference in overall stiffness of a beam specimen with $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2$ mm and a beam specimen with $t_1 = 3.2$ mm and $t_2 = 6.4$ mm is relatively small. However, stresses in the adhesive in these two specimens with seemingly equal stiffness are vastly different. One possible reason for this difference may be that the adhesive stresses at the joint ends are more influenced by the difference in the deformations of the two substrates. For example, when substrate 1 is twice as thick as substrate 2, it does not deform as much as substrate 2 and, therefore, the specimen end deflection is principally due to the deformation of substrate 2. On the other hand, when substrate 1 is half as thick as substrate 2, the specimen end deflection is principally due to the deformation of substrate 1. From the standpoint of reducing stresses in the adhesive, the former is more desirable than the latter.

FLEXURAL FATIGUE EXPERIMENTS

Several beam specimens with single lap joints shown in Fig. 1 were constructed and tested in deflection-controlled flexural fatigue mode using a plate bending fatigue machine (Model LFE-150, Fatigue Dynamics). In this machine, the free end of the cantilever beam specimen is pin-connected to a crank arm and is deflected up and down using an eccentric rotor. The fixed end of the cantilever beam specimen was clamped to a 70 mm long x 50 mm wide x 6.25 mm thick aluminum plate, which in turn was bolted to the vise of the fatigue testing machine. The SRIM material available for experimental work was 3.2 mm thick. Since thicker SRIM plates were not available, two SRIM plates were bonded together to increase the substrate thickness.

The deflection amplitude used in the fatigue tests was varied from 10.2 mm to 25.4 mm. The only specimens that could be tested with ± 25.4 end deflection in the fatigue testing machine were the single layered substrates, i.e., with $t_1 = t_2 = 3.2$ mm. Smaller deflection amplitudes were used for the other specimens. Since the fatigue test was deflection controlled, the load acting at the crank end of the specimen to produce the preset deflection reduced with increasing number of cycles as fatigue damage appeared either in the joint, the substrates or both. The load could not

be measured directly; instead strain monitored by strain gages mounted on the aluminum plate was used as an indirect measure of the damage developed during fatigue cycling.

Failure modes observed in various beam specimens under flexural fatigue testing are summarized in Table 3. The first series of fatigue tests were conducted with beam specimens containing single layer of SRIM on each side of the single lap joint, i.e., $t_1 = t_2 = 3.2$ mm. The deflection amplitude was 25.4 mm. All these specimens showed damage at location 1 and 2 (Table 3) on both top and bottom surfaces of substrate 1. There was no visible damage either in the adhesive or in substrate 2. The surface damage in substrate 1 is mostly normal to the axial stress direction and appears to be either matrix cracks or fiber-matrix interface cracks. The appearance and accumulation of surface damage reduced the specimen stiffness. Since the fatigue test was deflection controlled, a reduction in specimen stiffness gradually decreased the maximum and minimum loads on the specimen. This resulted in a progressive reduction in the strain range with increasing number of cycles.

Beam specimens with $t_1 = t_2 = 6.4$ mm, i.e., with double substrate thickness on both sides of the joint failed by fiber tear in the adhesive joint. These specimens were cycled with a deflection amplitude of either 10.2 or 15.2 mm. Fiber tear was initiated at location 3 in substrate 2. There was no evidence of surface damage in either substrate. With $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2/6.4$ mm, failure was also by fiber tear similar to that observed with $t_1 = t_2 = 6.4$ mm. In sharp contrast to the specimens in which only surface damage occurs during fatigue testing, the strain range drops very sharply as fiber tear appears and continues to reduce thereafter as fiber tear continues to grow along the lap length.

Beam specimens with $t_1 = 6.4$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2$ mm were cycled with a deflection amplitude of 17.8 mm. In this case, surface damage was observed in substrate 2 just outside the joint area in the first 10,000 cycles and there was no visible damage in the adhesive. Finally, several beam specimens with $t_1 = 6.4/3.2$ mm and $t_2 = 3.2/6.4$ mm were tested with deflection amplitude of either 17.8 mm or 22.9 mm. One of these specimens with lap length equal to 12.7 mm was subjected to ± 22.9 mm cyclic deflection. The other two specimens with lap length equal to 25.4 mm were subjected to ± 17.8 mm and both failed by the failure of substrate 2 at the joint edge.

The fatigue study has demonstrated that failure in SRIM beam specimens with a single lap joint along its length depends on the substrate thickness, which, in turn, controls the beam stiffness. Depending on the beam stiffness, failure can take place either in the joint area or outside the joint area. One critical point in substrate 1 is the outer surface point in contact with the aluminum support where the axial stress σ_{xx} has a high value in tension. This is the location where fatigue damage was observed in specimens with $t_1 = t_2 = 3.2$ mm. For $t_1 = t_2 = 6.4$ mm, failure occurred by the fiber tear mode at the interface of the adhesive and the substrate. Although the axial stress is also very high at the support point, the peel stress, in this case, has a very high value. Therefore, fiber tear is a possible failure mode in this case; however, which failure mode will initiate first will depend on the relative magnitude of the stress and the strength associated with that failure mode. For example, with $t_1 = t_2 = 6.4$ mm, fiber tear occurred first before any surface damage appeared in either substrate 1 or substrate 2. This occurred possibly because the maximum peel stress in the adhesive exceeded the peel strength of SRIM before the maximum axial stress in the substrate exceeded the SRIM's fatigue strength. To predict the actual failure initiation, a lot more information is required on the strength properties of the substrate, adhesive as well as adhesive-substrate interface.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has demonstrated the importance of substrate stiffness on the stress distribution, maximum stresses as well as failure modes in SRIM composite beam specimens containing a single lap joint along its length. Maximum stresses in the adhesive depend not only on the overall beam stiffness, but also on the relative difference in substrate stiffness on two sides of the joint. The usual practice of stiffness matching between substrate 1 and substrate 2 may not be effective when the single lap joint is subjected to flexural loads. Depending on the substrate stiffness, flexural fatigue failure can be either substrate surface damage, fiber tear or substrate failure. At the onset fiber tear, a large change in the overall beam stiffness occurs, which can be detected by monitoring strain on the beam support structure.

REFERENCES

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Table 1: Maximum Stresses (in MPa) in Adhesive at the Adhesive-SRIM Interface
(at Specimen End Deflection = + or – 25.4 mm)

Substrate Thickness t_1 (mm), t_2 (mm)	Interface $A_1B_1C_1D_1$					
	σ_{xx}		σ_{yy}		τ_{xy}	
	Up	Down	Up	Down	Up	Down
3.2, 3.2	-179.8	189.6	-92.9	99.8	-34.5	42.9
6.4, 3.2	-111.8	114.8	-57.6	68	-23.4	27
3.2, 6.4	-381.4	353.8	-207	193.3	-94.3	66.1
6.4, 6.4	-314	309.3	-173	170	-64.4	78.8
6.4, 3.2/6.4	-268	253	-140	137.9	-53	63.8
6.4/3.2, 3.2/6.4	-311	327	-216	221.7	-99	78.3

Table 2: Comparison of Forces Required to Cause 25.4 mm Deflection
in Various Beam Configurations

Thickness		FEA	Force (N)	
Substrate 1	Substrate 2		Strain Gage	% Difference
3.2	3.2	2.92	2.65	9.25
6.4	3.2	5.9	5.51	6.6
3.2	6.4	5.2	4.8	7.7
6.4	6.4	14.8	13.73	7.2
6.4	3.2/6.4	13.7	12.65	7.7
6.4/3.2	3.2/6.4	11.19	10.15	9.2

Table 3: Failure Modes in Flexural Fatigue Testing

Thickness (mm)		Lap Length (mm)	End Deflection (mm)	Cycles Tested	Failure Mode
t ₁	t ₂				
3.2	3.2	12.7	±25.4	23,250	Surface damage at locations 1 and 2
3.2	3.2	12.7	±25.4	18,700	Same as above
3.2	3.2	12.7	±25.4	12,600	Same as above
6.4	6.4	12.7	±15.2	7,900	Fiber tear at location 3 adhesive interface
6.4	6.4	12.7	±10.2	355,200	Same as above
6.4	6.4	12.7	±10.2	37,000	Same as above
6.4	6.4	12.7	±10.2	27,800	Same as above
6.4	3.2/6.4	12.7	±10.2	6,300	Same as above
6.4	3.2	25.4	±17.8	11,700	Surface damage at location 4
6.4	3.2	25.4	±17.8	-----	Same as above
6.4/3.2	3.2/6.4	25.4	±17.8	2,100	Failure in substrate 1 at location 5 at the joint edge
6.4/3.2	3.2/6.4	25.4	±17.8	-----	Same as above
6.4/3.2	3.2/6.4	12.7	±22.9	-----	Failure of substrate 2 at location 6 after fiber tear was initiated

Fig. 1: Basic specimen configuration used in the flexural loading study.

Fig. 2 : Stress distributions at the adhesive-substrate interface (left) and at the adhesive mid-thickness (right) for both substrate thickness = 3.2 mm when the specimen is deflected downward.